

Social Safety Net Program in Bangladesh: A Case of Ekti Bari Ekti Khamar Project

*Md. Bakhtiar Uddin

Abstract:

The study explores various aspects of Ekti Bari Ekti Khamar Project of the government of Bangladesh based on literature review and filed survey in two upazilas of Mymensingh and Meherpur district. With some shortcomings, as the study suggests, the micro-credit based project is functioning well in reducing poverty in the rural areas. There are high rates of non-poor inclusion in the selection of beneficiaries. However, in terms of ownership of land, error inclusion is minimal. Most of the respondents reported that they invested the credit in income generating activities. Although, project's priority is investing in agriculture at homestead, few (12.5 percent) households invested in this sector. Most of the households (45.83 percent) invested in small business. On an average monthly income of the beneficiary households increased by Tk. 2,573 by investing the average credit of Tk. 9,000. The project's commendable success lies in creating small savings and building up saving mentality. Empowerment of woman and creation of social awareness among the rural mass are the important issues. Poor people are very much enthusiastic in the program because of low interest charge, saving contribution from government and flexible repayment installments. Ineffective inclusion of beneficiary hinders well functioning of the village development organization. Among other problems, nepotism and influence from local political leaders are identified as major setbacks.

Key words:

Poverty, contributory micro-savings, micro-credit, revolving fund, credit, installment, farming, error selection

1. Introduction

Bangladesh is a poor country. One third of the population lives under the poverty line (GoB, 2012). To uplift poor people from poverty Bangladesh government is undertaking many programs. Currently, Bangladesh government is running as many as 98 social safety net programs (GoB, 2013). As part of social safety net program the government has initiated Ekti Bari Ekti Khamar (One House One Farm) project under social empowerment category in July, 2009. The project aims at poverty alleviation, enhancement of food production and increase of social awareness. Contributory micro-credit and cooperative organization are set as instruments to achieve the targets. Target group of the project is hard core poor and poor people. The project envisages that every house will turn into a farm as targeted people will farm with the training and micro-credit provided by the government.

2. Methodology

For conducting the study both primary and secondary data have been used. Primary data were

*Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, Jatiya Kabi kazi Nazrul Islam University, Trishal, Mymensingh.

collected in some villages under Trishal Upazilla of Mymensingh district and Mujibnagar Upazilla of Meherpur district. Village organization members in each area were chosen randomly for interview. Thirty member households of the project from two locations were interviewed. The interview was conducted in March, 2013. A well structured questionnaire was designed and properly pre tested to avoid error in data collection. Along with questionnaire method, Focus Group Discussion (FGD), and key informant interviews were taken place. The researcher himself attended several village organization meetings, called *Uthan Baithak*. In-depth interviews with upazilla coordinator, field organizer, village organization manager were also organised. For collecting secondary data upazilla office's record and published booklet on the project were reviewed.

The author is an Assistant Professor, Department of Economies, Jatiya Kabi Kazi Nazrul Islam University, Trishal, Mymensingh.

3. Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study are :

- (i) to analyze the socio-economic impact of the project;
- (ii) to evaluate the operation of the project; and
- (iii) to find the shortcomings of the project.

4. Overview of the Project

Alleviation of poverty is very crucial for Bangladesh. Although different programs were taken to eradicate poverty, at present nearly 31.5 percent people live below the poverty line (GoB, 2012). However, the pace at which poverty is being alleviated is very satisfactory compared with the other south Asian countries. The existing poverty cycle can be broken if the poor are allowed to have access to resources, and justice is ensured. Micro-credit is recognized as a suitable strategy to transfer resources to the poor people in Bangladesh. There is a broad consensus in the literature that participation in micro-credit schemes has contributed to reduce the vulnerability of poor households (Morduch 1998, Zaman 2004, Khandhker 1998, and Khandhker et al., 1998, cited in WB 2006). Reducing vulnerability of the poor paves the way of poverty reduction. Keeping these facts in mind the micro-credit based project, named *Ekti Bari Ekti Khamr* has been undertaken to enhance the status of the rural poor. The project has started its operation from July 2009. First phase of the project has been started operation since July 2009 and will be operating till June 2013. Second phase will start in June 2013 and end in June 2016. After completing the second phase it will continue its operation under Bangladesh Rural Development Board or an independent Rural Development Foundation. According to the project each house is considered as an economic unit. A Village Organization (VO) comprising 60 hardcore poor/poor members, of which 40 are female, is formed and each VO forms a Village Development Organization (VDO). Each member of the VDO deposits monthly TK 200 to his/her account; on the other hand same amount is credited from project fund as contributory micro-savings. Accordingly, each member's total annual savings becomes Tk. 4,800 in the first year of which Tk. 2400 is his own and Tk. 2400 is the project's contribution. At the end of the second year the cumulative saving is amounted to Tk. 9,600, and including interest it amounts to Tk. 10,000. In addition to that, every VDO gets

annually TK 1, 50,000 as capital incentive from project's fund. After two years total capital of each VDO becomes TK 900,000 which is used as revolving fund. From the revolving fund each member is granted loan. The project aims to provide micro-credit with the lowest possible rate of interest and the softest loan repayment condition. Interest rate is termed as service charge and which is flat 8 percent on the loan. Loan repayment installment could be weekly, monthly, semi-annually or annually, as decided by VDO. It also stimulates generation of savings by giving contributory micro-saving incentive. Before allowing credit members are given direct or indirect training on farming such as agriculture, aquatic culture, livestock, nursery, and poultry. The borrowers are expected to invest the credit-amount in different farms established around their homesteads. Each VDO arranges a weekly/monthly meeting namely *Uthan Baithak*. In the meeting a wide range of VDO related and other societal agenda are to be discussed such as health, nutrition, sanitation, family planning, corruption, law and order of village, village development issues, income generation activities, and so on (Project booklet).

5. Socio-economic Characteristics of the Respondents

Out of 30 respondents, 12 persons were taken from the villages of Trishal upazila of which 3 persons were female and the rest 9 were male. The remaining 18 respondents were taken from the villages of Mujibnagar Upazila of which 13 persons were female and the rest 4 were male. All but one respondent were married. Average age of the respondents is 39 years. About 33 percent of respondents have no education. Education level of literate respondents ranges between class 5 to 10. On an average each respondent has 2.62 children. It is reported that every household is male-headed.

6. Errors in Beneficiary Selection

According to the project implementing guideline (Booklet) the following categories of households are to be considered as target population.

- (i) Poor women-headed households owning 0- 50 decimals of land (Priority-1);
- (ii) Poor households owning less than 0.30 acre of land (Priority-2);
- (iii) Poor households owning maximum land up to 0.50 acre (Priority-3); and
- (iv) Poor households in char land owning maximum 1 acre of land (Priority-4).

Leakages and targeting errors are common in almost all social safety net programs in Bangladesh. There are problems with selection of beneficiaries. There are inconsistencies between the different criteria listed in the Implementation Guidelines and also between the criteria defined and the objectives set for the program (Khuda, 2011). World Bank study on major social safety net programs in Bangladesh found the prevalence of inclusion errors (WB, 2006). Ahmed (2004a) and Ahmed (2000b) found that 11-47 percent of the beneficiaries of Primary Education Stipend Program (PESP) program of social safety net were non-poor and incorrectly included in the program. Errors in inclusion and exclusion prevail in other programs as well. The present study also reveals the existence of inconsistency in the selection of target beneficiaries with the above selection criteria. It is found that on an average each of the respondent household had 9.6 decimals of homestead land and 60.28 decimals of cultivable land. Only 20 percent of respondents, along with their own land, had hired land on share cropping. In terms of ownership of land, 8.33 percent

households were selected erroneously in Trishal upazila whereas the corresponding figure was 5.55 percent in Mujibnagar upazila (Table 1). However, if monthly income was considered to measure poverty, the rate of error inclusion would be higher. According to Barkat (2012), almost 60 percent of beneficiary households of public safety net programs in Bangladesh are non-poor. During FGD session, the VDO managers reported that maximum organizations have 20-25 percent richer members. If poverty is measured in terms of Cost of Basic Needs (CBN) definition, the error selection will be higher. According to CBN definition, the field survey depicts that the non-poor beneficiaries were 83.33 and 72.22 percent respectively in Trishal and Mujibnagar (Table 3).

Table-1: Land ownership status of the beneficiary households: Comparison with the selection criteria

Land ownership category	Trishal		Mujibnagar		Selection category
	No of households	%	No of households	%	
Only homestead	5	41.67	4	22.22	Satisfied priority-2
Up to 0.5 acre including homestead	4	33.33	4	22.22	Satisfied priority-3
Up to 2.5 acres including homestead	2	16.67	9	50	Satisfied priority-4
Over 2.5 acres	1	8.33	1	5.55	Error selection
N	12	100	18	100	

Source: Filed survey, 2013.

6.1. Income of the Respondent Households

Average household income in the surveyed households is estimated as Tk. 14,496. In most of the households, income is earned by the male family head only (76.66 percent). In 16.67 percent cases, income was earned by two members of the respective households and in 6.67 percent cases it was earned by three members.

Table 2: Income of the respondent households

Income range (Tk/mont)	No. respondents	%
4,000-7,500	4	13.33
7,501-9,000	4	13.33
6,001-15,000	12	40
Above 15,000	10	33.33
Total	30	100

Source: Filed survey, 2013.

To identify whether the respondents are poor or non-poor, two poverty lines are estimated. In the two locations two inflation adjusted poverty line incomes are calculated from Household Income and Expenditure Survey (HIES) 2010. According to HIES 2010 lower and upper rural poverty line incomes in Dhaka division were Tk. 1,497 and Tk. 1,756 respectively. And in Khulna division these were Tk 1,398 and Tk 1,683 respectively. Inflation is adjusted by 17.3 % considering Consumer Price Index (CPI) between 2010 and February 2013. If we consider the upper poverty

line, 16.67 percent households in Trishal upazila and 27.67 percent in Mujibnagar upazila were absolute poor. Thus, most of the beneficiary households in these two locations were non-poor.

Table-3: Households in terms of poverty lines

Poverty Line	Trishal(%)	Mujibnagar(%)	Non-poor inclusion	
Lower	8.33	16.67	Trishal	Nujibnagar
Upper	16.67	27.78	83.33%	72.22%

Source: Filed survey, 2013. The poverty lines were estimated from HIES, 2010 by the author.

7. Investment and Income Generation

On an average the borrowers received Tk. 9,000 as credit from the project. Income generation through micro-credit is one of the main objectives of the project. Most of the respondents reported that they invested the credit in income generating activities. Although, project's priority is investing in agriculture at homestead, a few (12.5 percent) households invested in this sector. Most of the households (45.83 percent) invested in small business. Investment in cultivation at outside of homestead accounts for 25 percent. To finance cost of overseas migration and medicare was reported by 8.33 percent and 4.17 percent respondents respectively. Only 4.17 percent of households used credit to buy sewing machine. By investing the credit amount, income of the borrowers went up by on an average Tk. 2,573 per month. In the case of some small traders, Income went up by as high as Tk. 10,000 per month. This increase in income indicates poverty reduction among borrowers. The contributory micro-credit played a role in building up savings. Almost half (46.67 percent) of the households had no previous savings. Most of the respondents reported that their attitude towards savings had been changed and willingness to save increased due to the involvement in the VDO.

8. Credit Repayment

Loan recovery rate varies from 40 percent to 100 percent depending on the nature of the VDO. Relevant officials of the project in Trishal upazila have noticed that the overall loan recovery rate in the upazila is 39 percent. It is also reported that the village organizations, which are relatively more politically considered and have more wealthy members, showed less recovery rate. Village organizations which have greater number of poor beneficiaries specially hard-core poor usually have higher recovery rate, and in some cases, it is 100 percent. However, key informants have noticed that doubt about the future of the project is a major cause for low rate of loan recovery. Many of the members have expressed doubt that if different political party assumes power in the next election, project may be stopped and saving deposits may not be paid back. Lack of supervision and monitoring are also reported responsible for low repayment rate. Shortage of manpower is reported as a major reason for low supervision of the utilization of credit. As the project officials have been recruited for the project period only, they don't exert effective effort in monitoring and evaluating the organizations.

9. Political Affiliation and Bribe

The female respondents in surveyed locations reported that they didn't have any idea about political affiliation in beneficiary selection or loan sanction. However, some male respondents (40

percent) reported that there was political affiliation. At the initial stage of the project implementation there were misconceptions among people. Many people believed that each member of village organization would be given one house and one farm as the name of the project. They also believed that *lakhs* of money would be given to them as credit. Keeping eye in this view many people gained membership of the village organization by paying bribe to the political leaders and to the chairmen of *Union Parishads* (UP). At the first phase of the project each of the village organization was given some fixed assets such as cow, hen, goat, corrugated tin to be distributed among the hard-core poor members of the organization. The FGD participants reported that there were much irregularities and political consideration in the distribution of these assets. Much of the assets was gone to rich and politically considered members. When the opportunist members came to know that only eight thousand or some little more amount of credit would be given to them, they stopped to deposit saving installments to village organization. Exerting political and administrative pressures they gained credit and immediately stopped paying back the loan installments. It is observed in the discussion with project official that inclusion of these politically motivated members hinders smooth running of each organization.

Box 1: Best and worst functioning VDO in Trishal upazila

Best-functioning VDO

Name: Birrampur/I)Darirampur Village Development Organization

Upazilla: Trishal, District: Mymensingh

Code ID: 61946601

Date of formation: 01/01/2012

Number of members: 60, Male: 12, Female: 48

Member's savings: Tk. 1, 80,000, Contributory micro savings (Govt's part): Tk. 1, 44,000

Loan fund received: Tk. 1, 12,500

Total fund of the organization: Tk. 4,36,500

Loan paid to 44 members worth of Tk. 3, 58,000

Loan recovery rate: 100%

Worst-functioning VDO

Name: Chikna Monohar Village Development Organization

Upazilla: Trishal, District: Mymensingh

Code/ID: 61948503

Date of formation: 01/01/2011

Number of members: 60, Male: 46, Female: 14

Member's savings: Tk. 1, 56,000, Contributory micro savings (Govt.'s part): Tk. 1, 44,000

Loan fund received: Tk. 2, 22,850

Total fund of the organization: Tk. 5,22,850

Loan paid to 26 members worth of Tk. 2,60,000

Loan recovery rate: 10%

This organization received initial grant in kind such as 5 cows, corrugated tin and hens.

Nature of these VDOs is different. In the first case most of members are female. It has been found that females are more responsive in case of loan repayment and income generation. Most of the members of this organization are hard core poor and member selection criteria are

strictly maintained here. No member was included here being pressurized from any quarter of the society. Previously, most of the members were dealing with other private micro-credit providing NGOs. They have no allegation with the amount of loan. They have found the program very advantageous and beneficial compared to other private NGOs.

Whereas, in the second case most of the members are male. Members came from richer section of the society. Many of them were included under political consideration. Some were reported giving bribe to local political leader in gaining membership of the organization. Those who received loan didn't repay installments along with personal saving properly. They believe that the loan is one type of grant from government, as like initial in kind grant, and will not have to be repaid. Because of low repayment rate, further loan sanction is not granted by the project official. Those who didn't receive loan they stopped depositing personal saving. Confusion and lack of trust is built among the members that hindered proper functioning of the organization.

Source: Upazilla office, *Ekti Bari Ekti Khamar* Project and FGD with VDO members.

9. Problems Identified

The respondents and stakeholders identified the following problems of the project:

- (i) *Small loan amount:* Initial loan disbursement to each member is as high as Tk. 10,000. But with this little amount no business venture can be run smoothly.
- (ii) *Change of Government:* From the experience it is found that a project run by one government may not be continued by another new government. There is a huge doubt among the members of the VDO that the project may not be continued if opposition political party comes in power.
- (iii) *Confusion regarding saving withdrawal:* There is a confusion among many of the members of VDO that untoward event may occur at the time of withdrawal of the savings, that they deposit each month, at the event of government change over.
- (iv) *Procrastination in loan sanction:* Loan is made out of the fund of each VDO. In case of low saving deposit and loan default the fund replenish thereby lowering the chance of new loan allocation which creates confusion among non-loan-receiver members.
- (v) *Nepotism and political consideration in loan sanction:* It is found that nepotism and political consideration take place at the time of granting loan which hinders the smooth running of VDO.
- (vi) *Shortage of manpower:* Due to lack of right amount of manpower it is difficult to monitor and evaluate VDOs properly.
- (vii) *Working Area:* It is reported that working area of each VDO is very large and 60 members are scattered within the area.

10. Recommendations

After analyzing the pros and cons of the project it is pertinent to put forward some recommendations. These are as follows:

1. Targeting efficiency of the project should be increased. Measurement of poor and hard core poor should be done in terms of monthly income along with ownership of land. Poor and hard core poor should be selected as members of the VDOs.
2. According to the target of the project it is expected that the loans received should be invested in farming, thereby increasing total agricultural production.
3. While existing VDOs are ward-based the project should consider forming the VDOs on village based, with 30 members instead of 60 members.
4. It is important to build VDO office/gathering/meeting place where members can gather and discuss with various aspects of their organization.
5. To remove bureaucratic tangles Upazilla level committee should be reformed comprising two officials, Upazila Nirbahee Officer (UNO) and Upazial Co-ordinator (UC). If so, it will be easy to conduct each step easily and to implement decisions quickly.
6. Efforts should be taken to build trust and confidence among the beneficiaries of VDO.
7. For better functioning of the project, it is quite imperative to remove nepotism and political consideration in every stage of VDO activities.
- 8 It is essential to increase manpower to monitor the activities of each village organization.
9. Incentives should be paid to the officers and VDO managers for smooth functioning of the project.
10. The project should be made permanent so that its official can exert maximum efforts.

12. Conclusion

Despite some drawbacks the project is functioning well. Although the project aims at increasing total production by farming in the homesteads, most of the beneficiaries of the project invest the loan amount in small business which plays a vital role in alleviating poverty in rural areas. On an average, income of each loan recipient increased by Tk. 2,573 per month which is very crucial for eradication of income poverty in project covered areas. In some cases the income was much higher than of the average. The project's commendable success lies in creating small savings and building up saving mentality among beneficiaries. The project is also contributing to empowering woman and raising social awareness among the rural mass. However, it is found that woman has little freedom in spending the loan received. Thus more emphasis should be given to the choice of the female member of the village organization in investing credit. Likely, all other safety net programmes in public sector this project has some targeting inefficiencies. If target beneficiaries are selected appropriately, the project will be able to contribute to the poverty reduction of the country to the optimum. Overall functioning of the VDO depends on nature and purpose of the members. It is found that among relatively poor members both loan recovery rate and utilization of loan is much higher. Therefore, it is expected that more emphasis should be given to poor people in selecting beneficiaries. There are some problems indentified. Among them small loan amount, procrastination in loan sanction, nepotism and political consideration are major ones. For the sake of sustainability of benefit from the project some necessary steps such as management of beneficiary selection, monitoring of investment, easing bureaucratic tangles, increasing office manpower should be taken.

References

1. Abmed, A.U. (2004a). "Assessing the Performance of Conditional Cash Transfer Programs for Girls and Boys in Primary and Secondary Schools in Bangladesh", Working Paper, IFPRI.

2. Ahmed, Shaikh (2004b). "Delivery Mechanism for Cash Transfer Programs to the Poor", Social Protection Discussion Paper Series 0520, World Bank.
3. Barkat, Abul (2012): "Improving the targeting effectiveness of the social safety nets in Bangladesh", working paper presented in the workshop on "Research to Inform Food and Nutrition Security Policies", held on 28 and 29 November 2012, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
4. Booklet: Ekti Ban Ekti Khamar project implementation guidelines, Rural Development and Co-operative Division, Ministry of Local Government and Rural Development, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
5. GoB(2013): Ministry of Finance, "Social Safety Net Programs, Budget 201 1-12, 2011-12 (Revised) Budget 2012- 13"
6. GoB (2012), "Bangladesh Economic Review", Ministry of Finance, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
7. Khandhker, S. (1998). "Fighting Poverty with Microcredit: Experience in Bangladesh", Oxford University Press, U.S.A.
8. Khandhker, S. and M. Pitt (1998). "The Impact of Group-Based Credit Programs on Poor Households in Bangladesh: Does the Gender of Participants Matter?", Journal of Political Economy, October 1998
9. Khuda, B, (2011). "Social Safety Net Programmes in Bangladesh: A review", Bangladesh Development Studies, Vol XXXIV, June 2011 ,No2, Dhaka, Bangladesh.
10. Morduch, J. (1998). "The Microfinance Schism ", Development Discussion Paper No. 626, Harvard University.
11. WB (2006), "Social Safety Nets in Bangladesh: An assessment", Bangladesh Development Series, paper no.9, World Bank Dhaka office, Bangladesh, January 2006.
12. Zaman, H. (2004). "The Scaling-Up of Microfinance in Bangladesh: Determinants, Impact, and Lessons ", World Bank Discussion Paper.